

violence and sexual abuse, Contraceptive measures; The expression of gender and sexual prejudice in the mass media, in public space; Dating violence and how to avoid it; Safe sex, healthy sex, responsible sex...

- Introduction of books and materials: 2 hours/session on topics such as sexually transmitted diseases and HIV; LGBT+...

- Art exhibitions, and exchanges with speakers, and experts to strengthen connections with students inside and outside the Thai Nguyen University of Agriculture and Forestry.

4.2. Discussion

- It is necessary to have close coordination between the Youth Union, the Student Union in the school, and the club so that the school students can update their knowledge about mental health and reproductive health.

- Towards replicating the student health club model in the coming time for the whole of Thai Nguyen University.

- Enhance the effectiveness of direct communication for the target audience, which is university students, focusing on communication with the participation of peer groups. When carrying out health education communication, it is necessary to illustrate many documents and pictures suitable for young people and communicate indirectly by distributing communication materials such as leaflets, handbooks, and communication through Fanpage, Facebook, and Instagram...

EDUCATION ON PREVENTING ETHNIC SECONDARY STUDENTS FROM CHILD MARRIAGE IN THE NORTHERN MOUNTAINOUS REGION OF VIETNAM

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Abstract

In this article, the author has mentioned the basic issues in education to prevent ethnic secondary students from child marriage, including objectives, contents, methods, and forms of education.

Keywords: child marriage, ethnic secondary student, education, mountainous region, marriage.

1. Introduction

Marriage means the establishment of a husband-and-wife relationship between a man and a woman in accordance with the law on marriage conditions and marriage registration. When performing a marriage, apart from the voluntary and mutual agreement between the man and the woman, one of the mandatory conditions that must be complied with is the marriage age as prescribed by law. According to the provisions of Clause 1, Article 8 of the Law on Marriage and Family (2014) of Vietnam, the marriage age for men is 20 years and more, and for women is 18 years and more [1]. This regulation is based on the study of socio-economic conditions in Vietnam in order to ensure the normal psycho-physiological development of young men and women, and it is important for them to be able to handle responsibilities in the role of a husband and a wife, a father and a mother when they step into a family

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life. Compliance with regulations on the marriage age is necessary for sustainable family happiness.

In the Northern mountainous provinces of Vietnam, the phenomenon of child marriage is still existing and has been causing many serious consequences both physically and psychologically for young people, adversely affecting the quality of the race, hindering the quality of life and socio-economic development, social progress, and sustainable development of ethnic areas.

In this article, we have mentioned the basic issues in education to prevent ethnic secondary students from child marriage, including objectives, contents, methods, and forms of education.

2. Contents

2.1. Objectives of education to prevent secondary students from child marriage in the Northern mountainous region of Vietnam

- To raising awareness for students in terms of the risks and consequences of child marriage. The school

propagates to help students understand the consequences of child marriage such as: Child marriage causes mental damage, health, and even life of students. Especially, child marriage degrades the race. Children born by child-married couples are often physically and mentally weak, thereby affecting the quality of human resources, increasing poverty and social inequality... [2]

- To help students identify the causes of child marriage, such as lack of understanding of legal knowledge, of the consequences of adolescent pregnancy and childbearing, especially outdated customs etc.

- To equip students with the knowledge of ethical standards and behavior in relationships, of the right to health and life protection, of the right to study as well as to be comprehensively developed in personality; to form the willingness and skills to fight against child marriage in students so that they know how to build positive relationships with people around them and become the core force in the fight against child marriage of which they themselves may be victims. Child marriage will not happen when students have the right awareness of reproductive health, of their own life safety, and when they have the skills to prevent this problem. If being well-trained, students will be an effective propaganda force to combat child marriage. Firstly, it is necessary to educate parents and the local community to understand the consequences and risks of early marriage, of having a baby at a young age.

Thus, it can be seen that, education to prevent child marriage in ethnic areas not only helps ensure a safe and healthy school environment, but also contributes to stabilizing social order and security, to reducing the risk of poverty, unemployment, illiteracy, the deterioration of social morality, as well as contributing to preventing the deviant behavior of part of young people.

2.2. Contents, methods, and forms of organizing education to prevent students from child marriage at the Ethnic Secondary Schools

2.2.1. Contents of education to prevent ethnic secondary students from child marriage

The contents of education to prevent secondary students from child marriage include:

- Knowledge of gender, marriage, family, and appropriate adolescent reproductive health to the age of secondary students.

- Knowledge, communication skills, and cultural behavior in relationships with the opposite-sex friends.

- Skills to identify and deal with the risk of child marriage.

- Skills to resolve conflicts with parents and the community when being forced to get married early (child marriage).

- Awareness of complying with the law, the Law on Marriage and Family.

- Awareness of fighting and condemning outdated customs and practices that infringe on children's rights and human rights regarding marriage and race maintenance.

- Educating on positive attitudes and behaviors in fighting against child marriage

- Introducing students to medical facilities, consultants, and psychological support when students have problems with reproductive health, difficulties in relationships with opposite-sex friends... which are not solvable by the schools.

2.2.2. Methods of educating on preventing ethnic secondary students from child marriage

In educating on preventing ethnic secondary students from child marriage, the following basic methods can be used:

- *Method of persuasion*: This method is used in teaching and educational activities to adjust students' awareness and attitudes, helping them behave appropriately in relationships. Especially, when detecting that the students are at risk of child marriage, educators need to convince students to realize the consequences of child marriage, thereby changing their mind and fighting against this problem and seeking for help to get rid of it.

- *Method of modeling*: In education to prevent child marriage, educators can use good examples of students who were determined to fight against child marriage to continue their learning, develop themselves and finally became successful grown-ups.

- *Method of observation*: This method allows those who get involved in educating students on preventing child marriage to detect the psychological changes of students during the conversation, thereby appropriately adjusting the way of influencing students.

- *The method of role-playing and handling situations*: This is a method to help students play the role of characters in the scenario under the topic of preventing child marriage which is built according to the purpose of the educator. This method helps students understand about child marriage more deeply. From the experience of role-playing, students are trained in these problem-preventing skills. Role-playing situations should be suitable for the topic of child marriage prevention education, suitable for age characteristics, life experience of students, and the actual conditions of the local community; At the same time, the situation should be open to different solutions for the students to find an appropriate one in order to handle it by themselves.

- *Method of rewarding, encouraging and motivating students*: This method is often used by administrators and teachers during the flag-ceremony hour at the first day of the week and in the class activities. On behalf of the school, the principal or homeroom teacher commends and encourages those who have gained academic achievements, actively and effectively participated in child marriage prevention activities. This method is aimed at motivating and encouraging students when they gain academic achievements and the achievements in the fight against child marriage.

- *Method of criticizing and punishing students*: In addition to rewarding and complimenting students, in education to prevent child marriage, it is also necessary to have strict and tough measures to warn students when they are at risk of child marriage, to help students think deeply about this problem, thereby self-regulating their behavior. When using this method, it is necessary to combine with other methods such as encouragement, persuasion, etc. to

make the highest efficiency in education to prevent students from child marriage.

- *Visual method*: This is a method by which teachers use visual aids and technical means in the educational process to prevent child marriage, in order to help students identify the problem and then take proper measures to solve the emotional difficulties and the problems of child marriage that they are facing.

Visual method can be used in the form of illustrations and videos associated with educational topics on prevention of child marriage or guiding students to express their thoughts and views about child marriage by drawings etc. thereby forming in students appropriate behavior to avoid danger and effectively fight against child marriage.

2.2.3. *Forms of organizing educational activities to prevent ethnic secondary students from child marriage*

In education to prevent ethnic secondary students from child marriage, some basic forms can be mentioned as follows:

- *Through teaching subjects* to help students self-consciously and systematically acquire the concepts of moral standards and lifestyle, in which the subjects of Literature, History, Civic, Biology are dominant in providing students with knowledge of appropriate behavior in relationships and reproductive health. Through class hours, the teachers who teach other subjects also play a great role in educating students' personality, helping learners form a scientific worldview, creating opportunities for learners to develop their positive emotions, to train their will, to perform duties and civic obligations, and minimize behaviors that are not in accordance with social standards including child marriage.

- *Education to prevent child marriage through self-training, self-improving and self-educating of each student*. The final result of the educational process is self-educating. Therefore, in education to prevent ethnic secondary students from child marriage, teachers need to arouse and stimulate self-discipline and positivity in students so that they can educate themselves and fight against outdated customs and child marriage.

- *Through school psychological support activities*: When students have psychological difficulties or are forced into child marriage by their parents, school psychological support activities help them overcome difficulties and find solutions to cope with the risk of being forced in child marriage. At the same time, thanks to these support activities, students' awareness of the problematic child marriage is enhanced, corresponding attitudes and skills to prevent child marriage are also formed and developed.

- *Through experiential and career-oriented activities*: Having students meet and discuss directly with "victims" of child marriage, thereby helping them to be deeply aware of the consequences of child marriage and teenage childbearing, consciously strive and train to develop themselves and actively fight to prevent child marriage.

- *Through the activities of the parents' association, local political and social organizations*: To prevent child marriage, it needs the cooperation of the whole society, the participation of local authorities, of socio-political organizations, and of the parents' association of each school. These forces cooperate with the school to organize propaganda activities, educate students to be well-aware of compliance with the Law on Marriage and Family, to be well-aware of protecting their own reproductive health, and to fight against child marriage so that they can live, study, and engage in the activities that are appropriate to their age characteristics.

The above-mentioned forms, to achieve effectiveness and positive results in education on child marriage prevention, must be implemented in a harmonious coordination between schools, families and society. The educational forces must be enthusiastic and responsible, and carrying out their activities in accordance with their functions and duties in an effective way.

3. Conclusion

Child marriage is a still common phenomenon in the Northern mountainous region of Vietnam, which has been causing many negative consequences for the physical and mental health of adolescents, hindering the socio-economic progress and development etc. Therefore, education to prevent ethnic secondary students from child marriage is an important task that secondary schools in the Northern mountainous areas of Vietnam need to pay attention to through various educational forms and diverse educational methods in order to help students have an in-depth awareness of the causes and consequences of child marriage, thereby forming in them the corresponding skills and attitudes to escape the risk of child marriage and actively fight against this problem.

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